

**INNOVATIVE CONCEPTS AND TECHNOLOGIES FOR ECOLOGICALLY SUSTAINABLE NUTRIENT
MANAGEMENT IN AGRICULTURE, AIMING TO PREVENT, MITIGATE AND ELIMINATE
POLLUTION IN SOILS, WATER, AND AIR**

**Key findings from the second round of the e-Delphi survey
on the use of nature-based solutions in agricultural
innovations.**

Report

WP6 Task 6.3. Policy-mapping, -codesign, & -recommendations

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SUMMARY OF THE REPORT

ESSRG undertook a rigorous e-Delphi process, recruiting an expert panel of industry leaders and scholars to thoroughly explore the key facets of implementing and evaluating the effectiveness of nature-based solutions in agricultural innovations. In this article, we present the results of a comprehensive process that aims to provide a deep understanding of the concept of nature-based solutions and agricultural innovations through best practices.

In our e-Delphi survey, we found that nature-based solutions (NBS) offer a range of practical agricultural practices designed to reduce nitrogen, phosphorus, sediment losses, and greenhouse gas emissions on a landscape and catchment scale. These practices, which are particularly relevant to agricultural, agronomic, dairy, poultry, and cattle production, are inspired and nurtured by nature, offering cost-effective strategies that yield environmental, social, and economic benefits while fortifying resilience.

Based on the results of the 2nd round of eDelphi we can conclude that most effective and feasible policies to support the spread of Nature-based solutions in agriculture are the following:

- ❖ Organised field/farm field days to showcase pilot studies, new technologies,
- ❖ Trainings: farm/field days, flyers, magazines
- ❖ Regulatory policies
- ❖ Requiring a nutrient management plan

These policies are both effective and feasible according to the experts.

According to our expert survey, the **main barriers preventing farmers** from adopting nature-based solutions (NBS) in agriculture are:

- ❖ Lack of **financial support**,
- ❖ **Lack of information** about the possible role of NBS,
- ❖ **High costs of investments** related to new practices using NBS, and
- ❖ **Lack of technical support.**

Surprisingly finding new markets, or the lack of knowledge on the new practices using NBS are much less a challenge.

We also found that the **most influential actors** in the adoption of nature-based solutions (NBS) in agriculture are **policymakers, regulatory bodies, and academic institutions**. In contrast, SMEs, private companies, independent advisors, and agricultural and rural development extension services currently play a more limited role in the implementation of NBS.

BACKGROUND

On our understanding of NBS:

In our survey, NBS encompasses a spectrum of agricultural practices geared towards reducing nitrogen, phosphorus, sediment losses, and greenhouse gas emissions on a landscape and catchment scale. These practices are particularly pertinent to agricultural, agronomic, dairy, poultry, and cattle production. Aligned with the European Commission's definition, NBS are solutions inspired and nurtured by nature, offering cost-effective strategies that yield environmental, social, and economic benefits while fortifying resilience.

Round 2 of the e-Delphi Questionnaire

The 2nd round of e-Delphi focused on NBS's policy environment. We aimed to assess the perception of measures supporting the implementation of NBS in agriculture. To understand the innovators' perspective the questionnaire had 4 main focal points where the participants were asked to rate on a scale of 1 to 7 the different options. The 4 main parts of the questionnaire were: (1) the possible barriers in the way of implementing NBS; (2) the feasibility; (3) the effectiveness of different measures; and (4) the different actors' agency in the implementation of measures.

In the following report, we present the results of Round 2 that closed on April 15 2025.

FEASIBILITY AND EFFECTIVENESS OF THE POLICIES

With the results of the 2nd round e-Delphi we were able to identify the policies that are feasible and effective according to the innovators and experts. We can then interpret these results in light of the main challenges and actors.

Figures 1 and 2 provide an overview of the effectiveness and feasibility of measures. Overall, all the policies are considered effective and feasible, as they received scores above 4.5. The most effective measure is Close collaboration between and among SMEs/private companies, government (local, regional, national), extension workers, academics and researchers, and especially the farmers/producers (5.9). At the same time, the most feasible is training: farm/field days, flyers, magazines (5.73).

Figure 1.: The effectiveness of the different policy measures

Figure 2.: The feasibility of the different policy measures

In the following list we developed a typology of the policy instruments, based on feasibility and effectiveness:

High Effectiveness / High Feasibility "Quick Wins":

- ❖ Trainings: farm/field days, flyers, magazines
- ❖ Organized field/farm field days
- ❖ Regulatory policies
- ❖ Requiring a Nutrient Management Plan
- ❖ Defining guidelines for pesticides/manure
- ❖ Information sharing
- ❖ Technology transfer

High Effectiveness / Low Feasibility "Strategic Priorities":

- ❖ Close collaboration among stakeholders (highest effectiveness, low feasibility)
- ❖ Defining strict emission & water quality limits

Low Effectiveness / High Feasibility "*Easy but Limited Impact*":

- ❖ Informal meetings of farmers' groups
- ❖ Subsidies for the use of NBS

Low Effectiveness / Low Feasibility "*Low Priority*":

- ❖ Formation of watershed/catchment groups
- ❖ Pollution taxes
- ❖ Cost-sharing of the use of NBS

To assess which measures would most support the implementation of NBS in agriculture according to the experts, we have created a matrix showcasing the results together. In the following matrix, we visualised the differences between feasibility and efficiency.

Figure 3.: On the most feasible and flexible policies to adopt NBS in agriculture

With the matrix, we can compare each policy in light of its feasibility and effectiveness which will allow us to proceed with Round 3 of the eDelphi. The **four most feasible and effective policies** are:

- ❖ Trainings: farm/field days, flyers, magazines;
- ❖ Organized field/farm field days to showcase pilot studies, new technologies;
- ❖ Requiring a Nutrient Management Plan;
- ❖ Regulatory policies.

Out of these 4, there was a smaller difference between the effectiveness and feasibility in the case of measures enhancing training and field days. Regulatory policies and requiring a nutrient management plan were considered more effective than feasible.

On the lower half of the chart are the measures that are **neither feasible nor effective** compared to the others:

- ❖ Formation of watershed/catchment groups;
- ❖ Implementing taxes for pollution;
- ❖ Cost-sharing of the use of NBS (farmers share the cost);
- ❖ Close collaboration between SMEs, government, extension workers, academe, farmers.

The latter is worth highlighting, as it was considered the most effective, however it was one of the least feasible.

ON THE CHALLENGES

Figure 4.: on the challenges of implementing NBS in agriculture

According to the responses, all the barriers listed were challenging (they received a score above 5). The most challenging barrier was the lack of financial support (5.93), closely followed by the lack of information about the possible role of NBS (5.86). This provides ground for our 3rd round of eDelphi questionnaire, which will partly focus on knowledge gaps. The least challenging barrier was finding new input providers (5.00). The barrier with the highest standard deviation was the high costs of investments related to new practices using NBS, which was the third most challenging barrier, correlating with the lack of financial support.

ON THE AGENCY OF DIFFERENT ACTORS

Figure 5.: on the importance of the actors implementing NBS

Similar to the findings on challenges; all the actors listed were deemed important (with a score above 5). The most important actors in the implementation of NBS were the policy-makers and regulatory entities (5.97). They were followed by the academy/researchers who are responsible for testing/validating NBS in experiments (5.76). We can conclude that actors of the private sector were found less important than policymakers and researchers.

NEXT STEPS

The third round will focus on knowledge gaps and policy recommendations. It will be open from May 20th to May 31st.

The e-Delphi will be followed in June 2025 by a webinar to test the overall results of this research task.

METHODOLOGICAL BACK-GROUND

We collected 30 completed questionnaires from various experts and researchers to gain insight on the measures that support the implementation of NBS in agriculture. Most of our participants have a background in science with a PhD degree; however, we also received answers from experts in the farming and NGO sectors. Our respondents were from 10 different countries.

SCIENTIFIC BACK-GROUND

[ECONUTRI](#) is a European Union Horizon Europe innovation project that aims to develop innovative concepts and technologies for ecologically sustainable nutrient management in agriculture, to prevent, mitigate, and eliminate pollution in soils, water, and air. The general objective of ECONUTRI is to optimise, validate, and demonstrate novel NBS adapted into a holistic concept.

The primary objective of this report is to harness the collective expertise of industry leaders and scholars through an eDelphi methodology. Through three rounds, we aim to delve into key facets of NBS implementation and effectiveness in agricultural innovations:

- ❖ Round 1: understanding the concept of NBS and agricultural innovations through best practices.
- ❖ Round 2: existing & desired policies, challenges, enabling & hindering factors.
- ❖ Round 3: knowledge gaps & policy recommendations.

Disclaimer

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